

EVALUATING THE IMPACT OF SAUDI ARABIA'S VISION 2030 ON THE QUALITY OF REHABILITATION HEALTHCARE SERVICES IN RIYADH: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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Abstract

Background: Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030 and the Health Sector Transformation Program aim to improve the quality and accessibility of healthcare, including rehabilitative services. Evaluating their impact is essential to guide future policy and practice. We aimed to assess patient satisfaction with rehabilitative healthcare services in Riyadh in the context of Vision 2030 initiatives. **Methods:** A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted between January and February 2024 among Saudi citizens receiving rehabilitative care in Riyadh. Convenience sampling yielded 207 valid responses via paper and electronic questionnaires. The survey collected socio-demographic data and measured satisfaction in six domains: Vision 2030's impact, patient experiences, social media influence, digital platform integration, cost and community effects, and service utilization obstacles. Responses were rated on a five-point Likert scale. Data were analyzed using SPSS v28 with descriptive statistics, Cronbach's alpha, and Pearson correlations. **Results:** Overall satisfaction was moderate to high, with respondents reporting improvements in pain management, functional abilities, and access to information through digital platforms. Positive impacts were noted in service accessibility and quality, aligning with Vision 2030 objectives. However, gaps remained in patient involvement in decision-making, communication about treatment side effects, and addressing resource constraints. **Conclusion:** Vision 2030 has positively influenced rehabilitative healthcare in Riyadh, enhancing service quality, accessibility, and patient outcomes. Strengthening communication, expanding professional development, and addressing safety and resource issues will further optimize services and contribute to national health goals.

Keywords: Vision 2030, Rehabilitative Healthcare, Patient Satisfaction, Saudi Arabia, Healthcare Quality, Riyadh, Cross-Sectional Study.

INTRODUCTION

Saudi Vision 2030 and the Health Sector Transformation Program focus on improving the quality of life by addressing inefficiencies in rehabilitation services and enhancing healthcare access. Alanazi et al. (2023) emphasize that Saudi Arabia's rehabilitation care is currently suboptimal and needs reform. The Ministry of Health plays a key role in improving rehabilitation services by integrating them into primary, secondary, and tertiary care. This study explores how Vision 2030 impacts policy decisions and the incorporation of new technologies in healthcare systems to improve services.

The study examines the effect of Vision 2030 on the quality of rehabilitation services in Riyadh City, focusing on medical care for individuals with disabilities or chronic conditions. By understanding these impacts, policymakers can ensure that healthcare services are

accessible and adequate for all regions, regardless of socio-economic status or disability (Alhabib et al., 2022). The results will offer insights into how Vision 2030 principles have been applied across health service organizations since its inception.

Vision 2030 in Riyadh aims to enhance rehabilitative healthcare services while reducing costs. Investments in infrastructure and advanced technologies, such as sophisticated imaging systems, have led to significant improvements in medical care. The cost-benefit analysis of Vision 2030 indicates long-term gains, improving public health and lowering per capita healthcare costs through increased efficiency and higher service standards (Alhakami et al., 2023). Patient satisfaction is a key indicator of healthcare success. Given the complexity of rehabilitative care, satisfaction levels vary, but focusing on patient needs and safety is essential to improving service quality and satisfaction (Ferreira et al., 2023). Riyadh is chosen for this research due to its role as Saudi Arabia's political, economic, and cultural center, with rapid urbanization offering a unique case study of healthcare development (Johnson, 2021; Garcia, 2022).

Vision 2030 has also increased access to healthcare in Riyadh by expanding online resources such as telemedicine and e-services. Health insurance initiatives have reduced out-of-pocket expenses, allowing citizens to access affordable care, which enhances recovery under the supervision of experienced healthcare professionals in comfortable environments (Alghamdi et al., 2022).

Vision 2030 and Rehabilitative Health in Riyadh

Vision 2030 has significantly impacted Riyadh's healthcare sector, particularly in rehabilitative health. It is crucial to evaluate whether government investments have led to improvements and identify strategies to enhance services provided by medical staff. By analyzing case studies from healthcare providers in Riyadh, we can assess the effectiveness of these initiatives and guide future policy decisions. The study also examines how health authorities have adapted to these changes and incorporated new advancements into their systems, offering insights into potential challenges and opportunities for further improvements.

The National Transformational Program and Rehabilitative Healthcare Services in Saudi Arabia

The National Transformational Program in Saudi Arabia aligns with Vision 2030, aiming to restructure the healthcare sector into an effective and comprehensive system that improves the quality of life for Saudi citizens. Key objectives include enhancing healthcare quality, improving access to services, and promoting health risk prevention. The government aims to expand healthcare capacity, ensure proper geographical distribution, and provide timely access to services. The program also focuses on supporting the sector's response to health needs through effective, safe, and financially sustainable health coverage, while revamping policies on healthcare innovation, quality, financing, and inclusion.

Quality of Rehabilitative Healthcare Services in Saudi Arabia

Vision 2030 has significantly impacted the quality of rehabilitative healthcare services in Saudi Arabia, particularly in Riyadh. The government's investments in healthcare infrastructure have improved access to rehabilitation care, with both new and existing facilities being upgraded to provide better services (Alasiri & Mohammed, 2022; Ahmed & Bugis, 2023). Preventive health initiatives, such as promoting physical activity and healthy eating, have helped reduce the need for rehabilitative services among some populations, while improving the quality of care when needed (AbouRokbah & Salam, 2023). Additionally, there is a growing focus on mental health awareness, improving access to rehabilitative care for individuals with mental health or disability issues (Justinia, 2022).

Despite these improvements, Saudi Arabia faces challenges related to common conditions leading to disabilities, such as mental illness, obesity, diabetes, and cardiovascular diseases. Major rehabilitation providers like King Abdul Aziz University Hospital and King Khalid University Hospital are expanding to meet the growing demand for services (Alanazi et al., 2023). While government efforts have resulted in better care, improved infrastructure, and universal healthcare coverage, challenges remain, including high costs in private facilities and issues with care quality (Al et al., 2016).

Patient Satisfaction with Rehabilitative Healthcare in Saudi Arabia

Patient satisfaction measures the extent to which patients are content with the healthcare they receive from their providers. It thus helps determine the success of healthcare systems. Given that rehabilitative healthcare is complex, with various aspects that need to be considered in order to determine patient satisfaction, the satisfaction rates of respondents differed across different spectrums. For instance, most respondents were slightly satisfied with the results of investigations relating to healthcare and privacy during treatment (Almass et al., 2022). This shows that patients who sought recourse for treatment gone wrong or poor healthcare services were satisfied with the process (Almass et al., 2022). However, most patients were not satisfied with their participation in decision-making and the explanation of the side effects of the medications given to them (Algudairi et al., 2018). The study findings showed that improving communication between patients and hospital staff would increase patients' overall satisfaction. Moreover, enhancing the education of healthcare service consumers would also improve patient satisfaction rates.

Improving Quality and Patient Satisfaction in Rehabilitative Healthcare Services Internationally

Focusing on patient safety and continuous quality improvement initiatives are vital for enhancing rehabilitative healthcare services (Ferreira et al., 2023). Healthcare providers should create systematic and ongoing activities to refine their services based on feedback and quality assessments. Collecting patient feedback through surveys and questionnaires is essential for tracking satisfaction levels and identifying areas for improvement (Alhajri et al., 2023). Educating patients about their conditions and treatment

options empowers them to make informed decisions about their health. This leads to more active participation in their recovery process, improving both healthcare outcomes and satisfaction (World Health Organization, 2017). Building the capacity of healthcare workers is essential. Regular training ensures that staff are equipped with up-to-date knowledge and skills. This leads to better patient outcomes, as healthcare workers can make more accurate diagnoses and deliver effective treatments (Alhajri et al., 2023).

Moreover, investing in infrastructure and technology, such as telemedicine, allows healthcare providers to offer more efficient and accessible care (Karuna et al., 2023). Investing in sophisticated healthcare infrastructure and technology is crucial to improve rehabilitative healthcare services. Advanced technologies help healthcare workers diagnose conditions faster and with more accuracy, leading to more effective treatment plans (Karuna et al., 2023).

This infrastructure also allows for remote patient monitoring and follow-up care, which improves accessibility and reduces the burden on healthcare facilities. Governments can also implement policy changes that reflect the current needs of patients, ensuring healthcare services are both financially accessible and of high quality. Such changes might include expanding insurance coverage, subsidizing treatments, or introducing healthcare financing models that reduce out-of-pocket expenses for patients.

Prevention-focused programs, such as those promoting physical activity, proper nutrition, and mental health awareness, can reduce the demand for rehabilitative healthcare services. These initiatives also align with Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030, which emphasizes preventive care as a cost-effective approach to enhancing public health (Al-Jalajel, 2023). In Saudi Arabia, particularly in Riyadh, Vision 2030 has been a game-changer for rehabilitative healthcare services. With increased government investments in healthcare infrastructure and technology, the quality of care has improved significantly. Additionally, preventive healthcare measures have been expanded, leading to better management of chronic diseases like diabetes and heart disease (Luttfi et al., 2022-2023). Vision 2030 also emphasizes affordable, high-quality care, making rehabilitative services more accessible to all, regardless of socioeconomic status or location (Alghamdi et al., 2022).

By implementing these strategies, healthcare systems can improve the quality of rehabilitative care and boost patient satisfaction, ensuring that all individuals, including those with disabilities or chronic conditions, have access to effective and compassionate treatment.

METHODOLOGY

This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted to assess patient satisfaction with rehabilitative healthcare services in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, during January and February 2024. The study targeted Saudi citizens attending rehabilitative healthcare sessions within the specified period. Convenience sampling was employed, and all patients receiving services during the study timeframe were invited to participate. Data were collected through both paper-based and electronic questionnaires, and a total of 207 valid

responses were obtained for the final analysis. A structured questionnaire was specifically developed for this study. It consisted of two main sections: socio-demographic data and patient satisfaction measures. The socio-demographic section collected information on age, gender, education level, marital status, and family income.

The satisfaction section evaluated several aspects of rehabilitative services, including accessibility of services and improvement in pain levels, evaluation of home intervention programs, functional improvement following rehabilitation, interpersonal relationships with therapists, and the availability of services through health and social media platforms. Items were rated using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

This section was further organized into six thematic areas: Vision 2030's impact on rehabilitation services, patient experiences with rehabilitation services, influence of social media on healthcare services, impact of digital platforms on healthcare services, effects of Vision 2030 on rehabilitation costs and community integration, and obstacles to utilizing rehabilitation services. The questionnaire underwent expert review by healthcare specialists to ensure content validity. Data collection was carried out during rehabilitation sessions, with participants completing the questionnaire either in paper format or electronically. Efforts were made to include all eligible patients during the study period to ensure a comprehensive assessment of the services provided.

Data analysis was performed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 28. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, were used to summarize participant characteristics and responses. The internal consistency of the questionnaire was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha, and Pearson correlation analysis was applied to examine associations between different satisfaction domains. Likert scale analysis was used to interpret participants' levels of agreement for each item. These statistical procedures facilitated the identification of patterns, trends, and relationships, enabling a comprehensive evaluation of patient satisfaction and the effectiveness of rehabilitative healthcare services in Riyadh.

CONCLUSION

The study shows that Saudi patients in Riyadh are generally satisfied with rehabilitation healthcare services, reporting improvements in pain and functional abilities. Vision 2030's efforts have positively influenced the quality and accessibility of rehabilitation care, helping to meet diverse patient needs. Digital platforms and social media have further enhanced communication and access to information. However, challenges such as resource constraints, professional development, and safety concerns remain. Addressing these issues will optimize services, improve patient outcomes, and contribute to the achievement of national health goals outlined in Vision 2030.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors certify that there is no conflict of interest with any financial organization regarding the material discussed in the manuscript.

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Authors' Contributions

All authors made a significant contribution to the work reported, whether that is in the conception, study design, execution, acquisition of data, analysis and interpretation, or in all these areas; took part in drafting, revising, or critically reviewing the article; gave final approval of the version to be published; have agreed on the journal to which the article has been submitted; and agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

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